

Fertilizer phosphorus requirement of rice and wheat grown on sodic soils

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Sodic soils, formed under the influence of sodium carbonate, are widespread on the Indo-gangetic plains of India. Sodic soils are nonproductive because of the high levels of exchangeable sodium, which causes the poor soil physical properties and high pH. Efforts are made to bring sodic soils under cultivation by the use of amendments and the adoption of appropriate agronomic practices. Because rice has high tolerance for excess sodium and has reclamation effect, it is recommended for cultivation on sodic soils during the initial years of reclamation.

Our knowledge of the dynamics of phosphorus (P), a major plant nutrient, during reclamation is limited; therefore this study was initiated to examine the P status of sodic soils and to identify the P fertilizer needs of rice and wheat grown on such soils.

A survey of the P status of barren sodic soils from many sites showed high amounts (15 to 68 ppm) of Olsen's extractable-P in the surface layer (0-15 cm), which decreased with depth and were highly correlated with the soils' electrical conductivity (EC).

To define the optimum P fertilizer needs of rice and wheat grown in rotation, a replicated field experiment involving P application to neither crop,

Effect of phosphorus application on the yield of rice and wheat grown in sodic soil. Karnal, India.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)							
	Rice				Wheat			
	1976	1977	1978	1979	1976	1977	1978	1979
R ₀ W ₀	5.0	6.2	5.4	5.4	2.2	0.9	2.9	3.0
R ₀ W ₅₀	5.1	6.0	5.2	5.9	3.1	1.1	2.7	3.2
R ₅₀ W ₅₀	4.8	6.0	5.4	6.0	3.6	0.9	3.0	3.4
C.D. at P = 0.05	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^aR = rice, W = wheat. Subscripts refer to P applications in kg/ha.

Effect of P application on the P status of an alkali soil under rice - wheat crop rotation. R = rice, W = wheat.

to rice, to wheat, and to both crops was initiated in 1976 on a barren, previously uncultivated sodic soil (pH = 10.3; EC = 4.6 mmho/cm, and Olsen P = 23 ppm). A rapid initial decrease in extractable-P after gypsum application and rice growth was due to the leaching of P to

lower layers and also to its immobilization to less-soluble Ca-P compounds (see table and figure).

For rice and wheat grown in newly reclaimed sodic soils, application of P fertilizer can be withheld for the first 3-4 years. ■

Effect of azolla manuring without incorporation

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Earlier trials conducted at PES revealed the possibility of saving 25 kg N/ha when a layer of azolla is incorporated into the soil before planting. The second crop raised in double-cropped wetlands can best use azolla. But because the farmer plants the second crop shortly

after harvest of the first, the growing and incorporation of azolla before planting are not possible. Therefore, growing azolla after planting was tried. Because the farmers do not practice line planting, incorporation of azolla is difficult. Therefore, azolla as dual crop was tried without incorporation.

In a trial conducted during the thaladi season of 1979, azolla was introduced as seed material at 3 t/ha a week after planting. Different levels of nitrogen — 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha — were tried with and without azolla but with

Grain yield of ADT31 in plots with and without azolla. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
N 0	3.0
N 0 + azolla	3.2
N 25	3.5
N 25 + azolla	3.6
N 50	3.9
N 50 + azolla	4.0
N 75	4.4
N 75 + azolla	4.5
N 100	4.8
N 100 + azolla	5.0
C.D. (P = 0.05%)	0.4